

Deliverable 7.2

Stakeholder engagement plan

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Deliverable 7.2 - Stakeholder Engagement Plan

1. Introduction

This document outlines the development and implementation of a multi-level stakeholder engagement plan, which will be developed as part of Task 7.2 “*Development and implementation of multi-level stakeholder engagement plan*” under Work Package 7 (WP7), with special focus on webinars which will be used as a vehicle to strengthen the engagement with stakeholders. Through this deliverable, WP7 aims to develop innovative solutions for targeting and communicating with relevant stakeholders, at multiple levels (primarily local and national). This work aims to enhance stakeholders’ understanding of 1) the challenges that affect the food system and the FOOD 2030 research and innovation (R&I) response, 2) the relevance of responsible research and innovation (RRI) and the food systems approach, and, importantly, 3) how stakeholders can take action within their own capacities and benefit from such an involvement. There will be close collaboration with work packages (WPs) 5 and 6 (Policy and City Labs, respectively), to ensure that particularly the learnings from the Labs are captured and integrated in the stakeholder engagement plan. The task foresees the development of tailored communication materials (webinars) to support the implementation of this plan and will be closely related to Task 7.6, which will focus on the sustainability of the stakeholder network and the FOOD 2030 Platform beyond the duration of FIT4FOOD2030. The stakeholder engagement plan will be based on current learnings, aiming for continued commitment of stakeholders at multiple levels.

2. Purpose

The FIT4FOOD2030 communication WP aims, on the one hand, to increase visibility and promote awareness of the project, including the FOOD 2030 policy framework, and advocate for the importance of RRI and systems thinking for food system transformation to a wide range of stakeholders and audiences. On the other hand, the aim is to engage stakeholders in a more targeted, hence meaningful way, to enhance the impact of some of the project’s specific activities and outputs.

Challenges thus far have included difficulties in adequately explaining the core objectives of FIT4FOOD2030 and its primary focus to stakeholders, in part due to the complex nature of the project; Furthermore, while operating at a central, EU level brings clear benefits with reference to the engagement of some stakeholders, it has also highlighted some challenges in identifying and reaching concerned local or national counterparts that could benefit from an involvement in FIT4FOOD2030.

The objective of the Stakeholder Engagement Plan is to ensure new and existing stakeholders with different interests in the project are reached, in a way that is meaningful to them. With this, WP7 will strive to ensure that the involvement of current stakeholders in the project is enhanced and continuously strengthened through the development of multiple webinars. To achieve this, the stakeholder engagement plan will build on the existing network of actors that the FIT4FOOD2030 project has developed (for example, through the existing Policy/City Lab networks) channelling communication through these networks to further build and strengthen the stakeholder networks. The objective of the (continued) stakeholder engagement plan, for which a linkage between Tasks 7.2 and 7.6 is foreseen, is threefold:

- To further and more meaningfully engage local and national stakeholders at multiple levels, focusing on the food system and the FOOD 2030 agenda;
- To reshape the FOOD 2030 Platform so that it becomes a two-way communication platform, providing additional opportunities for stakeholder engagement. This will ensure continued and increased engagement in the FOOD 2030 Platform beyond the life of the FIT4FOOD2030 project;
- To amplify the outreach and impact of specific project outputs and activities through the engagement with specific audiences, primarily via the Platform.

Complementing the communication and dissemination strategy

The foreseen webinars (D7.2) and online forum (D7.5) can be considered ‘vehicles’ for stakeholder engagement that support FIT4FOOD2030 to amplify the outreach to relevant audiences and disseminate specific project outputs and activities. As such, they complement the existing communicating and dissemination plan (D7.1), which has laid out a strategy to disseminate project outputs via the website, newsletter, social media, and particularly through the networks of partners. Some examples of project outputs that are being used for stakeholder engagement are the trend cards, EU Think Tank Policy Briefs, reports on R&I showcases and breakthroughs, videos, output from event such as the High Level event on World Food Day, other project deliverables, etc. For the sake of brevity, this deliverable will focus on the plans for development of the webinars as a vehicle to strengthen the engagement with stakeholders.

3. Outputs and division of tasks

WP7 will be submitting two deliverables centred around stakeholder engagement:

1. D7.2 Stakeholder engagement plan (M24)
2. D7.5 Plan for continued communication with stakeholders (M36)

These two deliverables are separate yet connected. For the successful creation of a Stakeholder Engagement Plan under 7.2, there needs to be sufficient value for stakeholders to engage in the first place. The FOOD 2030 Platform, in its current stance, lacks meaningful elements to foster engagement in a way that allows stakeholders to reap benefit from the Platform directly. The stakeholder engagement plan under Deliverable 7.2 therefore proposes to reshape the FOOD 2030 Platform so that it transitions from a one-sided communication tool to a two-way communication platform, providing more meaningful opportunities for stakeholder engagement.

At the same time, task 7.6 (linked to D7.5), focuses primarily on the sustainability aspect of the Platform; i.e. the continued engagement after the FIT4FOOD2030 project ends. Task 7.6 will be centred around the creation of the very ‘substance’ of the Stakeholder Engagement Plan, by reshaping the FOOD 2030 Platform into a new tool, centred on lasting impact and focused on interaction, co-creation and sharing.

a. Deliverable 7.2 (Task 7.2)

Under Task 7.2, WP7 proposes to develop a series of 4 webinars tailored to specific audiences. The webinars are the starting point from which to foster engagement in a different, more meaningful way, representing the first step in the transition from one-sided to two-way communication with stakeholders. The objective is to ensure the webinars:

- Are tailored to specific audiences (local, national, European)
- Are interactive and relevant
- Offer a concrete call to action
- Allow the FIT4FOOD2030 project to showcase and share its lessons learned and project outputs (CL modules, PL handbook, policy briefs etc), serving as a successful case for stakeholders to draw upon.
- Draw stakeholders towards the FOOD 2030 Platform

The webinars will focus on providing an overview of the food system challenges in relation to the different target audiences of each webinar. Overall, they will increase visibility and awareness of the project, the FOOD 2030 policy framework and FOOD 2030 Platform, advocate for RRI and systems thinking for food system transformation, and enhance the visibility and impact of specific project outputs (such as CL modules, PL handbook, Policy Briefs, Policy Cards etc). Each webinar will have (a) clear and specific call(s) to action and will be aimed at a different stakeholder group (primarily at local and national level). Finally, each webinar will conclude with a call to action to join the community of practice (developed under Task 7.6). The community of practice will provide stakeholders with a platform for two-way interaction, where discussion groups can be established, resources shared, and outputs from the FIT4FOOD project can be made visible and available.

The scope and communication messages of the webinars will be as follows (the format and outline are further explained below):

- To introduce the European food system, its challenges, and need for transformation to make them future proof;
- To introduce the concepts of R&I, RRI and the food systems approach;
- To introduce the FOOD 2030 agenda;
- To showcase FIT4FOOD2030 results as successful cases that stakeholders can draw upon where there is an interest to implement similar activities at local or regional level.
- To explain RRI in EU/national policy making, using practical examples from FIT4FOOD2030 Policy Labs, while promoting the Policy Lab handbook that will be developed in WP5;
- To explain RRI in the context of cities, using practical examples from FIT4FOOD2030 City Labs, while promoting the *educational modules* for City Labs that will be developed in WP6;
- To share the FIT4FOOD2030 learnings on stakeholder engagement at the level of cities, national ministries, and Europe/high-level;
- To launch a call to action to join the FOOD 2030 Platform and engage in the community of practice.

b. Deliverable 7.5 (Task 7.6)

This task focuses on continued stakeholder engagement after the project's end. Task 7.6 will be centred around the sustainability aspect of the FOOD 2030 Platform and proposes to develop an online, low maintenance digital platform in the form of a forum, allowing the community of practice to interact (D7.5). Here, stakeholders signing up to the FOOD 2030 Platform have a space to connect and engage via discussion forums, thereby enabling cross-sharing of knowledge and resources, including FIT4FOOD2030 project outputs. The community will encourage, enable and promote networking, discussions and collaborations within and between parties with similar focuses and scopes, thereby encouraging cross-sharing of information (e.g. discussion boards, promotion of events and webinars, sharing of resources, etc.). The community of practice can allow for the development of sub-communities, aimed at channelling more focused discussions and interactions among interested parties.

The main objective of Task 7.6 is:

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- To complement the objectives set out in Deliverable 7.2 under the Stakeholder Engagement Plan
- To ensure it delivers lasting impact, focusing on interaction, co-creation, sharing beyond FIT4FOOD2030's end.
- Under D7.5: to reshape the FOOD 2030 Platform into a two-way communication tool that is:
 - Self-sustained by the stakeholders themselves
 - the main way stakeholders interact/connect (with the project and each other)
 - the main way to showcase the project's outputs (creation of a toolkit).
 - The main go to place for stakeholders to search for relevant resources, upload new resources, find out about relevant events, engage in discussions etc.

4. Key Audience(s)

In line with the objective of the stakeholder engagement plan, namely to engage stakeholders in a targeted and meaningful way, the individual webinars will be tailored towards specific audiences locally, regionally and nationally, including the (interested) public, food chain actors, academia, policy makers/actors, stakeholder/citizen engagement organisations and NGOs. In the below described webinar formats, the specific main and secondary target audiences are indicated.

5. Impact & outreach

The expected impact of this work can be articulated in short-, mid- and long-term parameters and outcomes.

On a short term, the impact can be measured by the number of attendees to the webinars and the level of engagement during the Q&A sessions at the end of each webinar. Also, the number of views to the webinars afterwards, when uploaded to the FIT4FOOD2030 website, will be a quantitative measure of impact. Moreover, the webinars may impact the average number of registrations to the FOOD 2030 Platform, which will be assessed as well.

The expected impacts on this short term, though not measured, are a better understanding of 1) food system challenges and the FOOD 2030 R&I response, 2) the relevance of responsible research and innovation (RRI) and the food systems approach in the policy making process, and 3) how stakeholders can take action within their own capacities and benefit from that.

On a more mid- to long-term, the expected impacts will revolve around the actions that people take; some of these could be measured within the FIT4FOOD2030 project, such as the numbers of downloads of the City Lab educational modules, Policy Lab handbooks, registrations to the digital platform, number of interested people/organisations reaching out with questions and/or intentions to make use of FIT4FOOD2030's outputs, learnings and networks. Perhaps even an increased network of City and Policy Labs, self-sustained, may still happen within the project's lifetime.

Finally, on a long term, the wished-for impacts are a higher uptake of RRI and City and Policy Lab type of methods to facilitate engagement with stakeholders in the policy making process, and, ultimately, improved European food systems. It would, of course, be somewhat presumptuous to believe that these webinars alone would lead to a better food system, but our mindset and belief is that it will at least contribute, be it to a small degree.

6. Sustainability

Through Task 7.6 (D7.5), WP7 is planning to set up a community of practice to support the sustainability of the FOOD 2030 platform beyond the duration of FIT4FOOD2030. Learnings from the stakeholder engagement plan will be used, aiming for continued commitment of stakeholders at multiple levels. The community of practice will be promoted via the webinars, and stakeholders will be encouraged to utilise the platform to engage with similar audiences, thereby creating a space through which engagement and interactions can be fostered. The benefit of such a platform, besides facilitating outreach between stakeholders, is that it is low maintenance, increasing the likelihood of sustainability. The community of practice will also act as the main platform for resource-sharing and will act as a toolkit within which FIT4FOOD2030 project outputs can be stored and accessed, following the project's completion.

7. Proposed format of the webinar series

A series of four webinars will be developed, addressing the topics as outlined above. Although the individual webinars can be considered as 'stand-alone' and viewed separately, the first webinar entitled "*Responsible Research and Innovation in the food systems*" forms the basis on which the following webinars will elaborate.

Each webinar will have a similar structure with three pre-recorded presentations, followed by a live Q&A session with the three speakers. The pre-recording allows for an easy scheduling with the speakers and is less dependent on the internet connection during the live event.

Each webinar will start with a more general introduction, if possible, by a keynote speaker; this will raise the profile of the webinar and make it more attractive for people to attend. The idea of an external speaker is also to broaden the perspective beyond the scope of the FIT4FOOD2030 project, focus on the problems facing the food systems and (other) initiatives already happening, and to present FIT4FOOD2030 in the second and/or third talk as a case study and one of the (and not *the*) ways to address these challenges.

A professional company specialised in hosting webinars will be engaged. Also, a registration page will be put in place, which allows for sending reminders pre-event and for promotion of future webinars as well.

An overview of the four webinars is presented in Table 1 (below). The first webinar is expected to take place in November 2019, depending also on the availability of the invited speakers.

Table 1. Overview of webinars. Secondary target audiences are mentioned in brackets

Webinar 1: Responsible Research and Innovation in the food systems (Introductory webinar) Target audiences: policy makers/actors, academia, food chain actors (stakeholder/citizen engagement organisations, NGOs, CSOs, interested public, other)			
Timing		Talk overview	Speaker
End-January/mid-February 2020	Speaker 1 15 min	Overview of food systems and their challenges (global overview)	Keynote speaker. Options discussed (also with EC RTD) are Corinna Hawkes (Cardiff University) and Line Gordon (EAT Foundation)
	Speaker 2 15 min	Introduction to RRI in EU context	European Commission RTD (a colleague from Team John Bell/Karen Fabbri)
	Speaker 3 15 min	FIT4Food 2030 as case study; use of RRI in practice in Food Systems	VU (Jaqueline Broerse)
	Q&A - 15 min		
Webinar 2: RRI in policy making for future-proof food systems Target audiences: policy makers/actors at a national level (academia, food chain actors)			
March/April 2020	Speaker 1 15 min	Introduction by a policy maker on food systems, bringing up current systemic issues and potential solutions	*policy maker* (TBD with ZON). Note: this speaker could cover it from an EU perspective, while the next talks zoom in on a national level
	Speaker 2 15 min	PL example (F4F): - Motivation to join - PL experience	*PL focal* (TBD with ZON).
	Speaker 3 15 min	Call to action (reference to handbook and webinars)	(TBD with ZON).
	Q&A - 15 min		
Webinar 3: Cities as change agents: building competences for future food systems Target audiences: policy makers/actors at a local/regional level, stakeholder/citizen engagement organisations (food chain actors, NGOs, CSOs, interested public)			
May/June 2020	Speaker 1 15 min	Overview of challenges and importance of local engagement in the EU context	Roberta Sonnino?
	Speaker 2 15 min	Explain the concept of the City Labs and show the diversity and impact the workshops	CL (TBD with ECSITE)
	Speaker 3 15 min	Call to action (reference to handbook and webinars)	(TBD with ECSITE)
	Q&A - 15 min		
Webinar 4: Engaging with Stakeholders: learnings from FIT4FOOD2030 Target audiences: policy makers/actors, stakeholder/citizen engagement organisations, academia			
End September 2020	Speaker 1 15 min	Strategies for policy makers to engage different stakeholders. Learnings from EU TT	EU TT Focal (observations and learnings) – Maggie Gill?
	Speaker 2 15 min	Strategies for policy makers to engage different stakeholders. Learnings from PL coordinators	PL Focal (observations and learnings)
	Speaker 3 15 min	Strategies for policy makers to engage different stakeholders. Learnings from CL coordinators	CL Focal (observations and learnings)
	Q&A - 15 min		